

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE USE OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING MEDICAL CHEMISTRY TO STUDENTS OF I. HORBACHEVSKY TNMU

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the experience of using multimedia technologies as a mean of forming professional knowledge among medical students. The main types of multimedia types, which are used to organize the study of educational materials in medical chemistry, are highlighted. The most common multimedia hardware (computer, multimedia projector) and software (Moodle, ACS, MS Teams) technical tools used in teaching medical chemistry to students of I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University.

Keywords: multimedia technologies, educational process, medical education.

Introduction. The rapid development of information technology and the increasing maturity of computer network technology have made medical education more modernized, and the application of multimedia technology is one of the important symbols of medical education modernization [5].

The use of computer technologies significantly expands the possibilities that contribute to the assimilation of information and the activation of the cognitive activity of students [4]. They diversify traditional forms of education and increase motivation to study, which ultimately leads to obtaining thorough knowledge in the field of medicine [3]. The acquired skills lead to the formation of relevant competencies, which are an important factor in establishing the profession of a doctor.

The main aim of education for students of medical educational institutions is the acquisition of qualified and relevant knowledge. According to literary sources [1], about 80 % of information a person receives through the organs of vision, therefore, multimedia means are an actual supply of the educational material. An important condition for the introduction of multimedia technologies into the educational process in the training of future doctors is the presence of specially equipped study rooms with a multimedia projector and a computer for the teacher, a screen or a multimedia board and an environment in which the educational process takes place.

Organizing training sessions using multimedia technologies can save time by activating the presentation of learning materials by using multimedia tools available to any student. It can create a visualized colorful learning and play environment that has a truly revolutionary impact on students' perception of the subject throughout the training session [7].

Pedagogical aspects of the use of multimedia technologies and mobile applications in education are highlighted in the scientific works of S.S. Ryzhenko, YuChang Hsu, Yu-Hui Ching, Attewell J., Savill-Smith C., Douch R., Parker G, Traxler J., Thompson A., Kearney M., Schuck S., Burden K., Aubusson P and other [1, 8]. This demonstrates the unconditional interest of practicing teachers in finding other ways of more effective use of multimedia technologies. It has been demonstrated, by research on using multimedia

for learning, that there are more positive results observed in students who combine picture and words than those who use words only [2]. Furthermore, according to Guan et al. [4], several studies have established the importance of multimedia technologies to education and the widespread adoption of multimedia tools.

The objective of the study was to analyze the use of multimedia technologies as a mean of forming professional knowledge of medical students in the process of teaching medical chemistry; to describe the main types of information and communication technologies that are used in practical classes in medical chemistry at I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University.

Statement of the topic. Multimedia learning tools are a set of hardware and software tools that allow a student to communicate with a computer using graphics, sound, animation, video. Multimedia technology has some characteristics like integration, diversity and interaction that enable people to communicate information or ideas with digital and print elements. Multimedia has the potential for flexibility, interactivity, and integration of different multimedia educational information. Therefore, multimedia is a very useful and effective educational technology [7].

The study of a course "Medical Chemistry" at TNMU takes place in accordance to the Standard of Higher Education of Ukraine of the second (master) level of higher education, branch of knowledge 22 Health Care, specialty 222 Medicine and 221 Dentistry. Multimedia technologies in the process of teaching medical chemistry include material prepared independently by the teacher, presentation of information using the Power Point program, a video method, e-mail, electronic interactive boards, and others.

The following types of multimedia courses are used to organize the study of educational materials in medical chemistry: multimedia lectures, video lectures, interactive videos and electronic textbooks.

Multimedia lecture. An integral component of multimedia technologies in higher education is a multimedia lecture, which includes elements of the latest information technologies [1-2]. In the practical teaching work of the "Medical Chemistry" course, lectures-

presentations created using the Microsoft Power Point program are used.

When teaching the "Medical Chemistry" course, the teacher uses the following educational presentations:

- by the use of multimedia elements (visual, textual, combined);
- by the educational aim (presentation-demonstration, presentation-control);
- by direction (communicative with lexical dominant);
- by the form of work (individual, group);
- by origin (prepared by a teacher, prepared by a student).

For example, a teacher uses presentation-control when giving a final lecture on medical chemistry. This type of presentation makes it possible to systematize the knowledge of medical students and prepare them for the final inspection. A multimedia communicative lecture is demonstrated to students when teaching topics such as: "Solutions", "Fundamentals of titrimetric method analysis", "Dispersed systems".

The advantages of an educational presentation in the process of studying medical chemistry are:

- activation of students' attention and educational and cognitive activity;
- the teacher paying special attention to the logic of the presentation of educational materials, which has a positive effect on the level of students' knowledge;
- involvement of various databases (texts, tables, diagrams, video and audio fragments), which makes it possible to trace the development of a certain chemical phenomenon;
- increasing the quality level of the use of visualization, which helps students learn the topic more quickly and effectively;
- increasing the productivity of the lecture session;
- establishment of interdisciplinary connections.

Video lecture. The teacher records the lecture in Bandicam Portable/MS Teams/Power Point. Using the method of non-linear editing, it can be supplemented with multimedia applications that illustrate the presentation of the lecture. Such additions not only enrich the content of the lecture, but also make its presentation more attractive for students.

Figure 1. View of the video lecture "Dispersed systems" page in the Moodle system

The advantage of this method of the educational materials presentation is the possibility to listen to the lecture at any convenient time, repeatedly referring to the most difficult places. The teacher of the general chemistry department posts video lectures on the university portal, in the Moodle system.

Interactive video. Interactive video is a flexible technology, which combines text, audio, graphics, still pictures and motion pictures in one easy-to-use system that maintains learners' attention, require their participation and engages them in activities [1]. It is also a practical method for individualizing and personalizing instruction. Interactive video is a valuable learning system for tasks that must be shown rather than simply told, and a powerful active resource, especially for the educational situations in which the learner needs to interact with the instruction.

The use of interactive videos in the process of training future doctors helps to increase the level of independent assimilation of educational information, success and professional communication of students.

Electronic textbook. It is important to note that gadgets have become convenient tools for studying of medical chemistry materials. Students can download e-textbooks, dictionaries, case studies, etc [6]. Teachers

provide students with a list of links to electronic textbooks on medical chemistry according to the academic program. Electronic textbooks on medical chemistry provide mastery of the subject area due to easy access to the necessary information, quick search for the necessary information by keywords, viewing of animation and video fragments.

Multimedia technical tools implement multimedia technology and they are divided into hardware (computer, multimedia projector with built-in stereo speakers, TV tuners and sound cards) and software (programs and problem-oriented programming languages). The most common multimedia hardware and technical tools in teaching medical chemistry are a computer and a multimedia projector.

Computer. Medical chemistry study rooms are equipped with modern computers connected to a TV screen. This enables the teacher to have free access to the Internet, to demonstrate various chemical experiments and educational videos on the TV screen.

Multimedia projector. Modern technical tools make it possible to use a multimedia projector, which displays an image with a diagonal of up to 2 m on the

screen. This technological technique allows you to increase the quality of the use of visualization in practical and lecture classes on medical chemistry.

When teaching the "Medical Chemistry" course, teachers use not only multimedia hardware and technical tools, but also software tools (Moodle, ACS, MS Teams).

Moodle. The page of the educational course "Medical Chemistry" contains the entire range of educational materials that the student needs (syllabus, training program, thematic plans, lecture presentations, learning materials and resources, methodical guidelines to the training sessions, links to video lectures, audio and video materials, test control, etc). The Moodle system provides convenient tools for medical chemistry teachers, in particular: it allows to ensure individual work of the teacher with each student; evaluates the educational achievements of students; creates and saves

the portfolio of each student; allows you to develop an author's course.

Creating a medical chemistry page in the Moodle system contributes to the independent study of the course and the implementation of cognitive activities for students:

- providing the student with educational information and ensuring its awareness;
- comprehension of perceived materials, formation of concepts, formation of generalizations, assimilation of laws;
- consolidation and improvement of acquired knowledge, formation of abilities and skills;
- application of knowledge, skills and abilities;
- checking and evaluating the results of cognitive activity.

Figure 2. View of the Medicinal Chemistry page in the Moodle system

ACS. The result of the introduction of multimedia technologies into the learning process at I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University was the creation of an ACS system. The main aim of creating this system is to ensure the transparency of the educational process at the university. The ACS system

provides a number of opportunities: access to the schedule of students, teachers, courses and exams; availability of an electronic journal of success; to register a student for practice; creates a personal account.

The screenshot shows the ACS system interface for Ternopil National Medical University. The left sidebar contains navigation options: HOME, SERVICES, CABINET, SCHEDULE, JOURNAL (selected), Retake schedule, Retake registration, Thematic plan, Attendance statistics, ACADEMIC, DISTANCE LEARNING, INFORMANT, WORK PLAN, and LIST. The main content area shows the 'Journal' page for the 2022/2023 Autumn semester, Discipline: 'Медицина хімія: ММ-101, ММ-102, ММ-105, ...', and Group: 'ММ-115'. A table displays 11 practical sessions (Prac) with the following data:

№ заняття	1[Prac]	2[Prac]	3[Prac]	4[Prac]	5[Prac]	6[Prac]	7[Prac]	8[Prac]	9[Prac]	10[Prac]	11[Prac]
Theme											
Date	20.09	21.09	27.09	28.09	28.09	04.10	05.10	11.10	12.10	12.10	18.10
#	КЗХ	КЗХ									

Figure 3. View of the electronic journal page in the ACS system

MS Teams. MS Teams tools allow you to fully implement all components of the educational process, use innovative pedagogical approaches and methods. Thanks to multimedia tools and feedback, MS Teams enables remote participants to be present in the study room. The teacher has the opportunity to conduct interactive classes in more natural manner, using technologies for clear sound transmission, means of information exchange for joint and individualized learning.

The MS Teams platform is used by teachers to conduct remote lectures, practical classes and consultations on the "Medical Chemistry" course. The advantage of this multimedia program is that medical chemistry classes are held in real time and jointly (teacher-student) provides an opportunity to work on Word, Excel and PowerPoint files, etc.

The use of multimedia technologies in teaching medical chemistry contributes to:

- creation of dynamic interactive interaction between the teacher and students;
- activation of students' independent work with various electronic educational tools;
- increasing the attentiveness and activity of students;
- combination of learning processes and evaluation of learning results.

Conclusions. The modern model of training future doctors involves the introduction of modern information and communication technologies in accordance to world standards into the educational process. Using of multimedia technologies in teaching medical chemistry increase the motivation of the student, his cognitive activity are activated both consciously and unconsciously. The most effective are multimedia lectures, video lectures and electronic textbooks involving

multimedia software (Moodle, MS Teams, ACS). The organization of teaching using the electronic course "Medical Chemistry" created on the Moodle platform is aimed at improving the educational process of future doctors.

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